

Electrochemical study of *N*-2-[[5-(dimethylamino)methyl-2-furanyl]methyl]thioethyl-*N'*-methyl-2-nitro-1,1-ethenediamine.HCl (An histamine H₂-receptor antagonist Ranitidine hydrochloride) by direct current polarography

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Abstract The electroreduction of the histamine H₂-receptor antagonist Ranitidine hydrochloride has been studied in aqueous medium at dme. The effect of pH on this reduction has been studied in phosphate buffer in the pH range 2–9. The reduction of the nitro group to hydroxylamine gives two well-defined waves in the phosphate buffer in pH range 2 to 3.5 and a single well-defined wave was observed above the pH 3.5. The effect of concentration and temperature on half wave potential has also been investigated. The system was found to be irreversible and diffusion controlled. So the kinetic parameters (K^0_m , αn) have been evaluated using (M-I) and (G-B) method.

Keywords : Ranitidine hydrochloride, histamine H₂-receptor antagonist, electroreduction, DC polarography, kinetic parameters

Introduction

Histamine is a natural chemical that stimulates the stomach cells to produce acid. Ranitidine belongs to a class of medicines, called H₂-blockers that block the action of histamine on stomach cells, thus reducing stomach acid production, and thus useful in promoting healing of stomach and duodenal ulcers, and in reducing ulcer pain. Ranitidine has also been effective in preventing ulcer recurrence when given in low doses for prolonged periods of time. In doses higher than that used in ulcer treatment, Ranitidine has been helpful in treating heartburn and in healing ulcerous inflammation of the esophagus resulting from acid. It thus competitively inhibits the action of histamine on the H₂-receptors of parietal cell of the stomach¹.

Ranitidine hydrochloride (HCl) is a histamine H₂-receptor antagonist. Chemically it is *N*-2-[[5-(dimethylamino)methyl-2-furanyl]methyl]thioethyl-*N'*-methyl-2-nitro-1,1-ethenediamin HCl having following structure

Molecular formula C₁₃H₂₂N₄O₃S HCl

Molecular weight 314.4 g/mol

Ranitidine HCl is a white to pale yellow crystalline powder with slightly bitter taste and sulfur like odor. Freely soluble in water, methanol and ethanol, sparingly soluble in ethanol, very slightly soluble in chloroform and dichloro methane.

Literature survey reveals HPLC², TLC³, Visible spectrophotometry⁴, UV-spectrophotometry⁵, spectrophotometry⁶ and capillary electrophoresis^{7,8} methods have been reported for estimation of Ranitidine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical and bioequivalence and commercial formulation.

Voltammetry technique offers another possibility for the estimation of this compound. It appears from the lit-

erature that, no report has been made concerning the polarographic behavior of Ranitidine hydrochloride. The aim of the present paper is to study the electrochemical behavior of Ranitidine hydrochloride at dropping mercury electrode by direct current polarography.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride has been studied in phosphate buffer in aqueous medium. Reduction of nitro group in this medium gave two well defined waves at pH range 2–3.5 and a single wave was observed above pH 3.5. The reduction was found to be diffusion controlled.

For analytical determinations of Ranitidine hydrochloride buffer solution (pH 2.8) was chosen.

The reduction of the Ranitidine hydrochloride has been observed to be a complex process, involving four electrons for complete reduction of the nitro group to hydroxylamine.

A total of two electrons and two protons were involved in the formation of the nitroso (R-NO) intermediate, two more electrons and protons result in the hydroxylamine (R-NHOH).

Linear plots were obtained for $\log i/i_d - i$ versus $E_{d.e.}$ with various slope values. The varied values of slopes indicated that the reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride was irreversible. The kinetic parameters were calculated using Meites-Israel (M-I)⁹ as well as Gaur-Bhargava's (G-B)¹⁰ method.

The value of diffusion coefficient ($D^{1/2}$) has been determined by Ilkovic equation¹¹.

$$I_d = 607 n D^{1/2} C m^{2/3} t^{1/6} \text{ at } 25^\circ \text{C}$$

where, n = number of electrons transferred in the process, m = rate of mercury flow in mg/s, D = diffusion constant of depolarizer in cm^2/s , t = drop time in s, C =

depolarizer concentration in mille moles/liter and I_d = diffusion current in micro amperes.

According to them the equation for irreversible wave was found to be

$$E_{d.e.} = (0.05915/\alpha n) \log (1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}/D^{1/2}) - (0.0542/\alpha n) \log (i/i_d - i)$$

This may be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = [E_{1/2} - (0.0542/\alpha n) \log (i/i_d - i)]$$

$$E_{1/2} = (0.05915/\alpha n) \log (1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}/D^{1/2})$$

where, K_{fh}^0 = formal rate constant for forward reaction, D = diffusion constant and αn = transfer coefficient and other terms have usual significance.

Thus the value of αn was obtained from the slope of the straight line corresponding to $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$. The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{1/2}$ which were used to calculate K_{fh}^0 after getting the value of $D^{1/2}$ from the Ilkovic equation.

(M-I) has extended the Koutecky's graphical method into comparatively more precise mathematical form. Further, (G-B) has also extended the Koutecky's treatment for irreversible wave, since according to them the diffusion to the electrode surface (mercury drop) is spherical and not a linear one as assumed by (M-I).

(G-B) modification :

$$E_{1/2} = (0.05915/\alpha n) \log (K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2} / (\text{antilog } C) D^{1/2})$$

Effect of pH :

Reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride has been carried out at different pH (range 2–9) in phosphate buffer. Polarographic study of Ranitidine hydrochloride show two well defined waves in pH range 2–3.5 and a single, well-defined wave was at pH above 3.5. First wave height decreases with increasing pH and that of the second wave height increase with the increase of pH shown in Fig. 1.

The half wave potential shifts to more negative direction on increasing the pH, showing that the reduction becomes difficult at higher pH. Linear plots were obtained for $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ at every pH value. Variation of half wave potential and diffusion current with pH shows the involvement of proton in electrode reaction¹². Assuming that the rate determining step involves the transfer of four electrons, the value of slope indicates that the

Fig. 1. Reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride at pH (2.0-9.0).

reduction process is irreversible. From the value of K_{fh}^0 of first wave shown in Table 1, it is clear that, the degree of irreversibility increases as the pH value increases up to pH 3.5. From the value of K_{fh}^0 of second wave, shown in Table 1, it is clear that, the degree of irreversibility decrease as the pH value increases (upto pH 7), after which it increases again.

The number of protons, involved in the reduction process for each pH value was determined using relation^{13,14},

$$\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta pH = -0.05915 (Z)/\alpha n$$

where αn is the transfer coefficient. The value of αn is calculated from the following equation,

$$E = [E_{1/2} - (0.05915/\alpha n) \log (i/i_d - i)]$$

where i_d is the diffusion current.

Effect of temperature :

Titled drug exhibit two well defined reduction waves at all temperatures ranging from 288 to 308 K shown in Fig. 2.

The value of K_{fh}^0 at various experimental conditions comes out to be of the order of $10^{-7} \pm 3$ which indicates irreversible nature of reaction. The value of αn decreases with increase in temperature (Table 2). A decrease in value of αn implies that transfer of electron becomes difficult as temperature was elevated. Further the value of K_{fh}^0 increases with increase in temperature which suggests that irreversibility decrease with increase in temperature. This implies that reduction products of drug are stable at lower temperature. In other words the electrode reaction was rendered more irreversible at lower temperature.

Effect of concentration :

Polarographic study of Ranitidine hydrochloride at different concentration range from 1.5×10^{-4} to $6.0 \times$

Table 1. Effect of pH

Sl. no.	pH	$-E_{1/2}$ (V/S.C.E)	I_d (μA)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2}$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	αn	K_{fh}^0 ($cm s^{-1}$)	
							M-1 method	G-B method
(a) On 1st wave :								
1.	2.0	0.710	5.6	84.20	0.5196	0.6437	2.429×10^{-9}	3.292×10^{-9}
2.	2.5	0.730	5.4	76.78	0.4926	0.7059	4.136×10^{-10}	5.604×10^{-10}
3.	3.0	0.750	2.6	70.65	0.2372	0.7671	1.764×10^{-11}	2.391×10^{-11}
4.	3.5	0.772	1.4	67.93	0.1277	0.7978	1.958×10^{-12}	2.653×10^{-12}
(b) On 2nd wave :								
1.	2.0	1.049	5.9	74.08	0.5382	0.7316	2.261×10^{-14}	3.064×10^{-14}
2.	2.5	1.067	6.3	78.92	0.5747	0.6867	9.338×10^{-14}	1.252×10^{-13}
3.	3.0	1.078	6.7	80.93	0.6112	0.6697	2.839×10^{-14}	1.052×10^{-13}
4.	3.5	1.116	7.4	97.08	0.6751	0.5583	7.827×10^{-12}	1.065×10^{-11}
5.	4.0	1.182	9.3	119.95	0.8484	0.4520	3.121×10^{-10}	4.229×10^{-10}
6.	5.0	1.206	9.4	100.62	0.8575	0.5387	3.531×10^{-12}	1.606×10^{-12}
7.	6.0	1.275	9.5	105.84	0.8667	0.5122	3.128×10^{-12}	4.181×10^{-12}
8.	7.0	1.353	9.6	101.37	0.8758	0.5350	2.008×10^{-13}	1.266×10^{-13}
9.	8.0	1.420	10.2	69.91	0.9305	0.7753	9.003×10^{-20}	1.219×10^{-19}
10.	9.0	1.429	10.3	93.65	0.9396	0.5790	2.611×10^{-21}	5.181×10^{-20}

Fig. 2. Reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride at different temperatures (288-308 K).

Fig. 3. Reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride at different concentration (1.5×10^{-4} - 6.0×10^{-4} M).

Table 2. Effect of temperature

Sl. no.	Temp. (K)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V/S.C.E)	I_d (μ A)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	αn	K_{fh}^0 (cm s^{-1})	
							M-I method	G-B method
(a) On 1st wave :								
1.	288	0.755	3.4	84.70	0.3101	0.6398	8.373×10^{-10}	2.671×10^{-9}
2.	293	0.758	3.8	94.08	0.3466	0.5761	5.692×10^{-9}	7.713×10^{-9}
3.	298	0.765	4.4	99.22	0.4014	0.5462	1.372×10^{-8}	6.504×10^{-8}
4.	303	0.770	4.8	107.78	0.4379	0.5028	4.945×10^{-8}	6.732×10^{-8}
5.	308	0.773	5.6	112.83	0.5109	0.4803	1.070×10^{-7}	1.622×10^{-7}
(b) On 2nd wave :								
1.	288	1.086	8.0	95.65	0.7298	0.5666	1.442×10^{-11}	1.550×10^{-11}
2.	293	1.088	8.4	101.90	0.7663	0.5318	5.019×10^{-11}	6.801×10^{-11}
3.	298	1.092	9.8	106.32	0.8994	0.5097	1.387×10^{-10}	1.880×10^{-10}
4.	303	1.096	11.0	111.2	1.003	0.0487	3.702×10^{-10}	5.017×10^{-10}
5.	308	1.100	11.3	128.99	1.030	0.4201	6.292×10^{-9}	8.526×10^{-9}

10^{-4} in phosphate buffer (pH 2.8) was carried out. The effect of concentration on Ranitidine hydrochloride wave shown in Fig. 3.

The result indicates that the reduction is irreversible. The half wave potential shifts towards more negative value by increasing the concentration¹⁵, this behavior was observed in both waves, the height of the wave was found to vary directly with the concentration indicating the electrode reaction to be diffusion controlled. The values of K_{fh}^0 increases as concentration increases and irreversibility of reaction decreases that means the reaction is more irreversible at lower concentration. The results are shown in Table 3.

Thermodynamic parameters :

Thermodynamic parameters ($\Delta H_p^\#, \Delta H_v^\#, \Delta G^\#, \Delta S^\#$) have been reported in Table 4. The enthalpy of activation at constant pressure ($\Delta H_p^\#$) has been calculated by substituting the value of slope of the plot ($\log K_{fh}^0$ vs $1/T$) in the Vant Hoff equation¹⁶.

$$\Delta H_p^\# = 2.303 R \times \text{Slope}$$

where R = Gas constant.

The value of slope comes out to be 1×10^4

$$\Delta H_p^\# = \Delta H_v^\# + RT$$

From this relation $\Delta H_v^\#$ (enthalpy of activation at constant volume) was evaluated, the activation free energy

Table 3. Effect of concentration

Sl. no.	Conc. (M)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V/S.C.E)	I_d (μ A)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	αn	K_{fh}^0 (cm s^{-1})	
							M-I method	G-B method
(a) On 1st wave :								
1.	1.5×10^{-4}	0.760	2.5	63.38	0.2280	0.8551	9.314×10^{-13}	2.932×10^{-13}
2.	2.2×10^{-4}	0.762	4.7	75.74	0.4287	0.7156	1.027×10^{-10}	1.391×10^{-10}
3.	3.0×10^{-4}	0.764	6.2	77.28	0.5656	0.7013	1.960×10^{-10}	2.656×10^{-10}
4.	3.8×10^{-4}	0.773	7.0	76.73	0.6386	0.7063	1.489×10^{-10}	2.018×10^{-10}
5.	6.0×10^{-4}	0.777	7.8	81.23	0.7116	0.6674	4.823×10^{-10}	6.535×10^{-10}
(b) On 2nd wave :								
1.	1.5×10^{-4}	1.078	6.7	76.37	0.6112	0.7097	2.819×10^{-14}	3.820×10^{-14}
2.	2.2×10^{-4}	1.084	10.3	92.33	0.9396	0.5870	6.509×10^{-12}	8.820×10^{-12}
3.	3.0×10^{-4}	1.091	12.1	99.43	1.103	0.5451	3.862×10^{-11}	5.233×10^{-11}
4.	3.8×10^{-4}	1.103	17.2	101.26	1.569	0.5355	6.428×10^{-11}	8.708×10^{-11}
5.	6.0×10^{-4}	1.130	20.6	113.34	1.879	0.4783	5.428×10^{-10}	3.860×10^{-10}

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters of Ranitidine hydrochloride

Sl. no.	Temp. (± 1 K)	$\Delta H_p^\# \times 10^3$ (J/mol)	$\Delta H_v^\# \times 10^3$ (J/mol)	$\Delta G^\# \times 10^3$ (J/mol)	$\Delta S^\# \times 10^2$ (J/mol)
1.	288	153.6922	151.2978	32.68906	4.118358
2.	293	153.6922	151.2562	32.15289	4.064959
3.	298	153.6922	151.2146	30.42631	4.053299
4.	302	153.6922	151.1731	30.91666	3.968858
5.	308	153.6922	151.1315	30.46708	3.917675

change ($\Delta G^\#$) was determined by relationship,

$$K_{\text{fh}}^0 = (KT/h) r_0 \exp^{-\Delta G^\#/RT}$$

where K = Boltzmann constant, h = Plank's constant, r_0 = mean distance between depolarized ions in the bulk solution, R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature.

In general value of r_0 is taken as $2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^1$. The entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\#$) was calculated using following equation,

$$\Delta S^\# = (\Delta H_v^\# - \Delta G^\#)/T$$

The plot of $\log K_{\text{fh}}^0$ vs $1/T$ is found to be linear from the slope of which the values of $\Delta H_p^\#$, $\Delta H_v^\#$, $\Delta G^\#$ and $\Delta S^\#$ have been evaluated and presented in Table 4.

A perusal of the values of various quantities present in Table 4 shows that activation free energy change ($\Delta G^\#$) is positive at all the temperatures suggesting the non spontaneous nature of electrode process¹⁸. Positive value of $\Delta S^\#$ suggests that formation of activated state accompanied with the increase of entropy.

Experimental

A digital DC recording polarography (CL-357) was used to record the current-voltage curves. Measurements were performed with three electrode assemblies, dropping mercury electrode (DME) as working electrode, platinum electrode as counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode.

Capillary of 120 mm length and 0.05 mm diameter was used.

The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics $m = 2.422 \text{ mg/s}$, $t = 13.5 \text{ s/drop}$, $h = 60 \text{ cm}$. Elico digital pH meter (Modal-111E) was employed to measure pH of solution. The current responses and applied potentials were recorded at scan rate 100 mV/min .

The stock solution of Ranitidine hydrochloride (1.9×10^{-3}) was prepared in triply distilled water. Phosphate buffer (1 M) was used as the supporting electrolytes. All

the solutions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals (Merck and Sigma) in triply distilled water.

Ranitidine hydrochloride solution was prepared freshly every 6 days.

The working procedure for DC polarography was as follows :

(i) A 10 ml of experimental solution was placed in a polarographic cell and deoxygenated with nitrogen for 15 min.

(ii) Triton X-100 (0.001%) was added to suppress polarographic maxima.

(iii) The cell was placed in Haake type ultra thermostat (N6114) and the capillary was inserted in solution.

(iv) The currents were measured at various applied voltages.

(v) The data wave recorded using coupled software on a monitor.

(vi) These were further processed using excel.

Conclusion :

A simple and sensitive method was developed for the qualitative determination of Ranitidine hydrochloride. The wave given by titled drug was found to be diffusion controlled.

Reduction of Ranitidine hydrochloride showed that compound presents two irreversible reduction waves at pH 2–3.5 and only one above pH 3.5. The value of αn decreases with increase in temperature (Table 2). A decrease in value of αn implies that transfer of electrons becomes difficult as temperature was elevated. Further the value of K_{fh}^0 increases with increase in temperature which suggests that irreversibility decrease with increase in temperature this implies that reduction products of drugs are stable at lower temperature. In other words the electrode reaction was rendered more irreversible at higher temperature.

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